

ROLE OF SHAMANA AND SHODHANA CHIKITSA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF MANDALA KUSHTHA: A CLINICAL CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Mandala Kushtha is a subtype of Maha Kushtha characterised by circular, elevated, erythematous patches associated with itching and discoloration. It is primarily a Tridoshaja condition with predominance of Kapha. **Aim:** To evaluate the role of Shamana and Shodhana treatment in the management of Mandala Kushtha. **Methods:** A 57-year-old female presented with circular, discoloured skin lesions on right and left forearm with severe itching and firstly diagnosed as a fungal infection. She was treated with Ayurvedic formulations incusing Shamana and Shodhana Chikitsa on the OPD basis to balance vitiated Doshas and improving the quality of Dhatus. **Results:** After treatment, there was marked reduction in size, itching and scaling.

KEYWORDS: Mandala Kushtha, Virechana, Shodhana.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda classifies all skin disorders under the term Kushtha involving concurrent vitiation of all three Doshas. Among the Mahakushtha, Mandala Kushtha is recognised as a persistent and relapsing entity characterised by White-Reddish plaques usually round in appearance, static, dense, often smooth and elevated.^[1] It is often compared with Tinea infection or dermatophytosis. It is a common superficial fungal infection of the skin, hair and

nails caused by *Trichophyton*, *Microsporum* and *Epidermophyton*. It presents with symptoms as erythema, scaling and pruritus. The main types of tinea include tinea capitis (scalp), tinea corporis (body), tinea cruris (groin), tinea pedis (feet), tinea manuum (hands), tinea unguium or onychomycosis (nails) and tinea barbae (beard area). Treatment of tinea involves the use of topical antifungal agents and proper hygiene and avoidance to predisposing factors. These limitations create need for safe, holistic and sustainable treatment approaches. Acharya Charaka asserts diseases treated through Shodhana therapy do not recur.^[2] In Mandala Kushtha, all three Doshas vitiated with Kapha involvement³ along with Rakta Dushti necessitate Shodhana as well as Shamana Chikitsa.

2. Methods

2.1. Patient Profile

- Age/Sex: 57-year-old female
- Diagnosis: Mandala Kushtha
- Treatment period: 28/2/2025 to 10/9/2025
- Past history: Chikungunya (7 years ago), LSCS (in 2005)

2.2. Chief Complaints

- Reddish discoloured circular patches on right and left arm since 1 year
- Severe itching
- Mild scaling
- Katishoola

Clinical Findings

Ashtavidha Parikshana

Table 1: Ashtavidha Parikshana of patient.

Nadi	Pittavataja
Mutra	Samyak Mutra Pravriti 4-5 times/day
Mala	Samyak Mala Pravriti 1-2 times/day
Jivha	Sama
Shabda	Spashta
Sparsha	Ruksha
Drika	Samanya
Akriti	Madhyama

Dashavidha Parikshana**Table 2: Dashavidha Parikshana of the patient.**

Prakriti	Pitta Vata
Vikriti	Kapha Dosha
Dushya	Twak, Rakta, Mamsa, Ambu
Satva	Madhyama
Sara	Mamsa, Asthi
Samhanan	Madhyama
Pramana	Madhyama
Satmya	Sarva Rasa
Aharashakti	Madhyama
Vyayamshakti	Madhyama

Other assessment

Nidana: Virudhanna Sevan, Ratri Jagran, Krodha, Diwaswapa, Ati Madhura Rasa Sevana, Vyasan like Mishri.

Purvaroop: Atiswedana, Gaurava, Vaivarnya, Klama

Samprapti: Hetusevana (frequently)→ Tridosha Prakopa→ Strotas Dushti (Anna, Rasa, Rakta) → Twak Adhishthan→ Mandala Kushtha

Intervention**Table 3: Shamana and Shodhana treatment given to the patient.**

Phase	Date and disease status	Intervention
1. Depana-Pachana	28/2/2025-27/3/2025 (60% improvement in reduction of symptoms)	Gandhak Rasayan 250 mg TDS Sariva Choorna 500 mg TDS Sootsekhara Rasa 250 mg TDS Kaishor Guggul 500 mg BD (After meals) Laghumanjishthadi Kadha 3 tsp BD Trivruttha Leha 1 tsp HS
2. Raktamokshana along with Shamana	28/3/2025-24/4/2025 (60% improvement)	Siravedha- Dushta Rakta 70 ml each from bilateral cubital fossa was let out. (28/3/2025) Trivanga Bhasma 60 mg TDS was added with above Internal medicines. Jeevantyadi Yamak was advised for local application.
3. Raktamokshana along with Shamana	25/4/2025-5/6/2025 (70% improvement but itching was prominent, Katishoola reduced)	Jalaukavacharana- on right forearm with one Jalauka, upto 25 ml was let out. (25/4/2025) Instead of Kaishor Guggul, Arogyavardhini 500 mg BD was prescribed with above medicines.
4. Shamanaa	6/6/2025-19/6/2025	Kaishor Guggula 500 mg BD was

	(80% improvement but Alpa Strava, Kandu and Daha was observed, Katishoola increased)	added instead of Arogyavrdhini. Sarivadyasava 4 tspBD was added instead of Laghumanjishthadi Kadha Rest of the internal medicines were same
	20/6/2025-17/7/2025 (Anupashaya in Kandu and Daha)	Kamdudha 500 mg TDS Yashtimadhu 250 mg TDS Sariva 250 mg TDS Sukshma Triphala 500 mg BD (After meals) Aragvadha Kapila Vati 2 tabs HS
	18/7/2025-14/8/2025	Gandhak Rasayan 250 mg TDS Trivanga 60 mg TDS Sariva Choorna 500 mg TDS Anupana- Khadirarishta 2tsp+ Syrup Rubyclin 2 tsp
5. Snehapana	15/8/2025-8/9/2025	Mahatiktaka Ghrita 20 ml for 20 days then 30 ml for 5 days was given. Internal medicines were withheld except Khadirarishta 2 tsp + Syrup Rubyclin 2 tsp was given in evening only.
6. Virechana	10/9/2025	Aragvadha Kapila Vati 2 tabs+ Erandsneha 20 ml was given. Virechanopaga Dravya- Ushnodak+ Mrudvika Patient had 8 Mala vega, Hina Shuddhi Samsarjana was advised.
7. Follow-up	26/9/2025 (90% improvement in the symptoms)	Mahatiktaka Ghrita 10 ml given for Shamanaa.

RESULTS

After Deepana-Pachana, slight elevation of Mandala Kushtha was reduced and there was overall 60% improvement in the disease. Before snehapana, Kandu and Daha was prominent and worsened July may be due to Varsha Ritu (Pitta Sanchiti). After Snehapana and Virechana, the itching and burning sensation gradually stopped and also there was marked improvement in discolouration of Mandala Kushtha.

images showing Mandala Kushtha Before and After treatment

Fig. 1: Mandala Kushtha on right and left forearm before Deepana- Pachana respectively.

Fig. 2: Mandala Kushtha on right and left forearm after Deepana-Pachana and Shamana Chikitsa respectively.

Fig. 3: Mandala Kushtha on right and left forearm after Virechana respectively.

DISCUSSION

In Sama Avastha of Mandala Kushtha. Deepana and Pachana was done. Gandhak Rasayan acts as Kaphaghna, Kledaghna and Raktashodhaka. Sariva Choorna and Kaishor Guggul reduces Raktagata Samata which results in Raktaprasadana. Sootsekhar Rasa causes Pitta- Kapha Shamana and Amapachan. Laghumanjishthadi Kadha acts on vitiated Kapha Dosha causing Rookshana. Trivrutta leha which is a Sukha Virechak was for Anuloman and Agnideepana. Siravedha was done for Dushta Rakta Nirharana reducing Kandu and Vaivarnya in the patient. Trivanga Bhasma acts as Vatapittashamak and has Rakta-Mamsa Gamitva.

Jeevantyadi Yamaka is a combination of both Ghrita and Taila which reduces scaling and herbs present in it like Manjishtha, Daruharidra have Kushthaghna and Raktashodhak properties promoting skin healing. When Kandu and Daha was more, Jalaukavacharan was advised for letting out Dushita Rakta. Arogyavardhini does Amapachan, Kledaghna karma which alleviates Kandu and has Rasa Raktagamitva. Sarivadyasava helps in improving discoloration, itching and local inflammation. For DahaShamana, drugs like Kamadudha, Yashtimadhu was advised. Sukshma Triphala has Sukshma Strotogamitva and Rasayana in nature. Khadirarishta was prescribed when Alpa Strava was observed in patient at Mandala Kushtha, this formulation causes Rookshana and alleviates excessive Kleda present in the body. Syrup Rubyclin causes Raktashodhan. Repeated Shamana chikitsa was given due to Punarudbhava of Vyadhi (recurrence), but Tikta Rasapradhana Aushadhi caused Rukshana Gunavridhi in the body and need for Snehan Chikitsa was observed. Also Acharya Charaka has stated that after Raktamokshana and doing Bahya and Abhyantara Shaman Chikitsa in Kushtha, one should go for Kalayukta Snehapana.^[4] After Shamana chikitsa, when Kala was suitable (Sharad Rutu), Virechana was planned. Mahatiktaka Ghrita Sneha was given in Shamana Sneha Matra. It's Tikta-Kashaya Rasa and Laghu; Sheeta properties are effective in pacifying Pitta and Kapha imbalances. Due to Snehapana, Doshasanchiti in Udara and Adhodoshagati was observed, Virechana by Aragvadh Kapila Vati and Erandsneha was given. Aragvadh Kapila vati is mrudu virechak and hence can be used for Nitya Virechan which helps in elimination of vitiated Doshas. Erandsneha has Ushna, Guru, Snigdha properties which causes Deepana at the level Amashaya, Amapachan at the level of Dhatu and Strotorodhahara at the levels of channels in the body and its Adhobhagahar properties helps in Virechana. Repeated Shodhana is advised in Kushtha Chikitsa. Again, Snehapana is advised to remove remaining Doshas.

CONCLUSION

This case demonstrates how a well-planned Ayurvedic treatment regimen can effectively manage Mandala Kushtha. By using individualized assessment and integrating both Shamana and Shodhana therapies, the approach successfully balanced the vitiated Dosha-Dushya, improved impaired Agni and reduced both systemic and skin related symptoms.

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